

Terraforming Saturn

Period of Time: 24th-25th century

Surface area compared to Earth: 83 times

Maximum population hosted after terraforming: \approx 600B+ citizens

Company involved in the process: **NAR** (Ndoni Advanced Robotics)

Number of robots involved in the construction of habitats after terraforming: 120B+

Purpose: after terraforming Saturn, build a habitat for more than 600 billion citizens to live on the planet using robots and advanced machinery.

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